

SELF-EDUCATION AS A MEANS OF SELF-DEVELOPMENT

Oskinbaeva.G.D

Karakalpak State University named after Berdakh

Summary: The article talks about the importance of self-education in self-development. Self-education is understood as a conscious and purposeful activity aimed at discovering, validating and improving personal qualities, skills, behavior and interactions with the outside world.

Key words: Self-education, needs, personality, individuality, subjectivity, individual, subject of activity, systematic, a culture of self-awareness

Self-education, as the most important means of self-development of a person, is purposeful and conscious under the influence of the ideas of the person about the results he wants to achieve. Self-education is a conscious and purposeful activity aimed at discovering, confirming and improving personal qualities, skills, behavior and interactions with the outside world. Like any activity, self-education is characterized by needs. Motivational framework, objectives, methods and results. The motivations for self-education are wide and varied, arising from different needs:

Kalit so'zlar: O'z-o'zini tarbiyalash, ehtiyojlar, shaxsiyat, individuallik, sub'ektivlik, individuallik, faoliyat sub'ekti, tizimli, o'zini o'zi anglash madaniyati

Ключевые слова: Самообразование, потребности, личность, индивидуальность, субъектность, индивидуальность, субъект деятельности, системность, культура самосознания

Rezyume: Maqolada o'z-o'zini rivojlantirishda o'z-o'zini tarbiyalashning ahamiyati haqida so'z boradi. O'z-o'zini tarbiyalash deganda shaxsiy fazilatlar, ko'nikmalar, xatti-harakatlar va tashqi dunyo bilan o'zaro munosabatlarni aniqlash, tasdiqlash va takomillashtirishga qaratilgan ongli va maqsadli faoliyat haqida so'z yuritiladi.

Резюме: В статье говорится о важности самодисциплины в саморазвитии. Под самообразованием понимается сознательная и целенаправленная деятельность, направленная на выявление, подтверждение и совершенствование личностных качеств, навыков, поведения и взаимодействия с внешним миром.

- in self-development: self-affirmation, self-improvement, self-realization;
- related to dissatisfaction with oneself, current situation;
- personal and authoritative nature: "Am I worse than others?", "I will not let others be ahead of me, I will still show what I am capable of!";
- caused by the desire to subjugate and manipulate others.

In any case, the need for self-education and the motivation for self-education are secondary. Even the presence of strong positive motives for self-development: self-affirmation, self-improvement, self-fulfillment are the motives of self-education. does not guarantee that it will appear automatically. Many highly motivated people want to improve themselves. Often, this process is not self-directed by nature; chance situations and opportunities presented by life are used to take at least one step forward in human development. A necessary condition for the emergence of self-education motives is the separation of self-education into an independent activity. This is possible only if you spend conscious goals, planning and certain voluntary actions. Therefore, self-education is a voluntary process that requires courage, dedication and determination from the individual. When a person develops habits of self-discipline, the level of will decreases, a real need for self-discipline is formed, and its satisfaction becomes individual and personal. Therefore, when organizing your upbringing, the first minutes are always the most difficult. The presence of expressed motives for self-education determines the uniqueness, that is, the uniqueness of setting specific goals for self-education. The goals, in turn, can be different. Often a person spends a lot of time discovering his personal strengths. In this case, the goal of self-education coincides with the goal of self-knowledge. Its difference is that the search for strengths is considered by a person as a factor of self-education, and not self-knowledge. The goal is often self-affirmation or self-improvement. Goals may differ in the object of self-affirmation and self-improvement, for example: development of certain personal qualities; mental processes (memory, thinking, imagination); abilities; the ability to communicate with people; specific skills needed to perform a specific activity, etc. Goals can be defined as derivatives of the desire to dominate, submit, or cooperate with others. Interestingly, self-discipline can also be renewed under the influence of fashion: "Everyone is engaged in self-improvement, but what makes me worse."

The list of these goals and the conditions for setting them by each person can be significantly expanded. However, this is not the case. The main thing is that, under the influence of positive motivation, a person is ready to set real goals for self-education and makes certain voluntary actions for this purpose, so that the value of setting goals corresponds to the value standards of this process. fits. In this case, the main condition must be met: setting goals for self-education should not be accompanied by self-denial, self-inflicted struggle with one's own shortcomings. Solving the problems of self-education and, through it, the tasks of development, is related to the complete and unconditional acceptance of the individual, otherwise self-education is self takes on the character of self-struggle, and self-development is

a (declared or undeclared) war with oneself. This is not the way to create personality, but to destroy it. Acquiring and mastering new things is a worthy way of self-education and achieving a positive result. In the context of the problem under consideration, methods and means of self-perception deserve special attention. Their analysis allows us to answer the question that is relevant for everyone on the path of self-education: how can I solve problems related to self-development? There are many such methods in modern science and practice. Let's look at a few of them. Self-motivation is a process, as a result of which a person independently determines the motives for engaging in self-education, evaluates all the positive and negative aspects of the results achieved and self-measures the benefits he received in the process of educating himself. An effective form of self-motivation is self-persuasion, if, using logical arguments, a person convinces himself of the need to change and develops the desired attitude. In some cases, even if he has convinced himself of the need to "start a new life", he has difficulties in implementing his plans; this is where self-regulation comes in handy as an effective means of overcoming obstacles. inherent inertia, laziness, etc. At the same time, if a person is considered lazy, he is not rejected, but is given a special time when he can fully express himself (for example, on Saturday from 17 to 20 hours). Self-motivation methods organically turn into self-programming methods at the second stage. In order to achieve results in self-discipline, you need an action program, for example: what do I do to stop conflict with others? What to do to develop your imagination? Based on the creation of your own program (even if it is written down, even if you can remember it), planning action is carried out: what needs to be done, in what order and in how much time. to achieve results. The next group is related to the methods of implementation of the program. It involves self-teaching techniques for specific future activities. For example, a person has a goal - to gain confidence in public speaking. Before the lecture, he can instruct himself how to: 1) mentally repeat the text of the speech; 2) convince yourself that his text is not bad and that others are not familiar with it; 3) mentally repeat the fact of performance, 4) do the necessary exercises to get rid of anxiety; 5) wait for the results of the performance, even if they fail (there is nothing wrong with this, life goes on and one failure does not change life). Such an attitude in itself gives confidence and power, and if the performance is really good, then it is reinforced and positively experienced by the individual. It also includes techniques: random self-observation of the process of self-development and implementation of plans, self-analysis and self-self-control, they together allow making the necessary corrections and development during the activity itself. future self-development program. Finally, it is important to analyze the results

achieved on a daily, weekly, year-long basis. Effective forms of describing what has been achieved and determining further prospects for the implementation of one's program are self-reporting and self-evaluation of the work done, acquired qualities and behavioral characteristics. Here, as we have repeatedly emphasized, reflexive mechanisms are involved, which are related to the subsequent self-prediction of personality development. On the basis of self-control, goals and methods of achieving results are adjusted. Self-knowledge is used as a tool for self-education. We remember that self-knowledge is an independent activity, on the basis of which self-development activities are launched, but it is a means of self-education, which it is carried out in cases where a person has identified a lack of knowledge about himself; allows one to analyze one's own activities, evaluate what has been achieved and set new goals for self-development; to analyze the characteristics of interactions with the social environment, where successes and failures are noted, requirements from others are determined, as a result, the further goals of self-affirmation and self-realization become clear again; self-education, which allows you to significantly expand your horizons about the world around you, understand your place in it, and gain the necessary knowledge as a basis for the further construction of your personality. As for the results, the level of their achievements is assessed individually by each person. There are cases when the result of self-discipline is significant, but a person is dissatisfied with it and sets new goals for himself. There are often cases when the result is modest, but the person is happy with it, because he did not expect such minimal success in the path of self-improvement. As for the social environment, society as a whole, their requirements are objective and do not depend on the experiences and complexes of each of its members, they are expressed according to the results of the requirements: what have you given for others? Society, What is your personal contribution to social development? Such an assessment is not directly formulated by anyone, but is consciously or intuitively implied by everyone who embarks on the path of self-development and self-education. is caught. And this creates a degree of satisfaction in what is finally achieved: the displeasure of a genius and the complacency of a common man.

It is recommended to raise the issue of the culture of self-education, characterizing self-education in the general sense as a means of personal self-development. The issue of the culture of self-education does not arise by chance and is related to the fact that everyone is engaged in self-education, but such activity is not always socially significant and causal subject to the laws. consistency in the self-construction of one's personality. The specified characteristics are the most important indicators of the culture of self-discipline. In fact, if a person engages in

self-education in order to improve the antisocial characteristics and qualities of the PERSON necessary to satisfy his selfish motives, the desire for power and domination over others, to destroy, suppress, harm others. if such self-discipline in society is in no way related to culture. The goals of self-education and thoughts must be noble, and the motives of self-improvement and self-realization are not only related to the demands of a particular society and society, but also to the 4 universal human related to values (for example, in totalitarian conditions). society, self-education in accordance with the ideals of this society will have value: instilling hatred towards the bourgeoisie as well as "enemies of the people" was welcomed under the Stalinist regime; arousing hatred for those who are not, other than oneself. - Aryan peoples were welcomed in Hitler's Germany, etc.). Thus, the culture of self-education is a desire to self-affirm and improve one's own characteristics and ways of behavior, interaction with universal ideals: Truth, Beauty, Kindness, Violence, etc. - and one way. the most complete self-awareness and self-realization of an individual. Another sign of culture is systematic self-discipline. Systemicity is the interdependence and interdependence of self-knowledge, self-education and self-development, each element of the system solves its own problem when solving, fulfilling their role, fulfilling the continuous process of self-realization and self-realization together. the individual in the changing circumstances of his personality. If self-discipline is carried out from time to time, if it deals with the individual without a clear system, without a material motivational basis, when the process of simple self-compulsion occurs through the will, such a self- self-discipline is ultimately fruitless. From this, if it is carried out under the discipline of self-discipline and correction of others (and it is rare to be in such conditions, for example, the daily use of parents, children do in the topic "How to develop your own will"). He goes through the process of self-education, and then as a process, disgust is instilled into him unnecessarily, and love as a duty. As control weakens, so does self-discipline. Consistency is the volition, permanence, interdependence that life effectively implements. Now let's turn to the structure of the culture of self-education, which includes: 1) the culture of choosing and setting goals for self-education; 2) culture of self-awareness; 3) culture of methods and means of self-education; 4) the culture of conditions in which self-education is carried out. The culture of choosing and setting goals for self-education consists of the ability of a person to set goals for self-education that correspond to the current situation (characteristics of personal development), which is determined by the stage of development of the individual. located - these are the goals of positive self-affirmation or positive self-improvement and self-realization. The setting of goals

should respond to the determined motivation, taking into account universal human values, as well as the suitability of motivation and goals to specific situations and environmental requirements, if these requirements are not antisocial in nature and do not fundamentally contradict people's attitudes and beliefs. From all of the above, it is clear that the formation of a culture of self-education in a particular educational institution creates a culture of setting goals for self-education in students, self-knowledge the culture of learning, the culture of choosing methods and means of self-education. First of all, it should be noted that the term "formation" is somewhat arbitrary. Formation does not directly mean the introduction of socially acceptable methods and means of teaching and self-education; formation means creating conditions (for example, creating an environment that allows solving the problems of stimulating processes at school). Self-knowledge, self-discipline and non-violent teaching of methods, methods, methods of self-discipline), to this person to build himself independently, provides an opportunity for self-affirmation and self-improvement. Self-awareness and self-development are subjective processes in themselves, however, they are subject to certain objective laws in their formation. Self-awareness develops within the framework of the whole self-awareness, which includes one's physical self, social self-identification, one's inner world, a holistic idea of oneself, o passes through stages of further individualization and development of self-awareness. Special attention is paid to the problem of forming a culture of self-education. The essence of self-education as a means of self-development is revealed, a general description of the culture of self-education of an individual is given, and the creation of a culture of self-education of educational institutions is given. information about the culture of self-discipline is provided through the implementation of its capabilities.

References

- 1.Абрамова Г.С. Психология только для студентов: Учебное пособие для вузов. – М.: ПЕР СЭ, 2001. – С.167
- 2.Абрамова Г.С. Психология только для студентов: Учебное пособие для вузов. – М.: ПЕР СЭ, 2001. – С.168.[]
- 3.Слободчиков В.И., Исаев Е.И. Основы психологической антропологии. Психология развития человека: Развитие субъективной реальности в онтогенезе: Учебное пособие для вузов. – М.: Школьная Пресса, 2000. – С.323.
4. Братченко С.Л. Экзистенциальная психология глубинного общения: уроки Джеймса Бюджентала. – М.: Смысл, 2001. – 197 с.
5. Абульханова-Славская К.А. Стратегия жизни. – М.: Мысль, 1991. – С.29.
6. Ананьев Б.Г. Человек как предмет познания. – Л.: ЛГУ, 1999. – С.154-162.
7. Ғозиев Э. Психология: (Ёш даврлари психологияси). – Тошкент: Ўқитувчи, 1994. –244б